

SCALE DEPENDENT FLUID MOMENTUM AND SOLUTE MASS MACROSCOPIC BALANCE EQUATIONS: THEORY AND OBSERVATIONS

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ABSTRACT

A mathematical development is presented concerning extensions to the macroscopic momentum balance equation for compressible Newtonian fluids flowing through saturated porous matrices, and the macroscopic mass balance equation of solutes transported with the fluids. It is shown that each of these balance equations is composed of a dominant macroscopic equation associated with a larger spatial scale, coupled with a secondary macroscopic balance equation valid at a smaller spatial scale. The dominant fluid momentum balance equation can govern the propagation of shock waves, conform to Forchheimer's law or to Darcy's law when friction at the solid-fluid interface is dominant. Concurrently, the secondary momentum balance equation is governed by inertia flow that conforms to a wave equation propagating the intensive momentum and the dispersive momentum flux, both deviating from their corresponding dominant average terms. The dominant macroscopic solute mass balance equation accounts for advection and hydrodynamic dispersion. The secondary macroscopic solute mass balance equation describes pure advection of the product of deviations from the average solute mass fraction and the average fluid density. Field observations under natural gradient flow conditions show excessive high concentration of colloids (average of 50 mg/L) under land irrigated by sewage effluents. The high concentration of colloids in a macroscopic flow field where specific discharge varies between 4 to 16 m/yr, is suggested to be due to the enhancement of colloidal mobility resulting from the secondary fluid momentum equation governed by inertia and the secondary solute mass equation of pure advection, both proven to be valid at a scale smaller than the one considered for spatial averaging.

1. THEORY

Application of averaging rules to a Representative Elementary Volume (REV) leads to the formulation of the macroscopic balance equations for interacting phases of fluids and a deformable porous matrix [Bear & Bachmat, 1990]. It was shown [Bear & Sorek, 1990] that during a certain time period due to the domination of inertial terms, the fluid momentum balance equation conforms to a nonlinear wave equation. Elaboration for the

case of thermoelastic porous media described the theoretical basis for obtaining displacement and shock waves [Sorek *et al.*, 1992]. These models, however, excluded the possibility of the exchange of microscopic inertia through the solid-fluid interface. Following [Sorek *et al.*, 1992, Levy *et al.*, 1995], additional microscopic inertia terms were introduced and a variety of nonlinear wave equation forms were obtained. In [Sorek *et al.*, 2005] we present the detailed development of the extended macroscopic Navier-Stokes equation. This describes the secondary coupled momentum balance equation comprised of momentum fluxes deviating from the averaged ones. Some of the averaging rules in [Bear & Bachmat, 1990] will be key elements in obtaining our extensions of the macroscopic balance equations. These, e.g., are:

$$\overline{e_{1\alpha}e_{2\alpha}}^\alpha = \overline{e_{1\alpha}}^\alpha \overline{e_{2\alpha}}^\alpha + \overline{\dot{e}_{1\alpha}\dot{e}_{2\alpha}}^\alpha ; \quad \overline{e_{1\alpha} + e_{2\alpha}}^\alpha = \overline{e_{1\alpha}}^\alpha + \overline{e_{2\alpha}}^\alpha , \quad (1)$$

where $\overline{e_{i\alpha}}^\alpha$ denotes the average over the α phase volume within ($\mathcal{U}$) that of the *REV*, of the i intensive quantity $e_{i\alpha}$ associated with the α phase and $\dot{e}_\alpha (= e_{i\alpha} - \overline{e_{i\alpha}}^\alpha)$ denotes deviation from the average.

In what follows we assume that:

[A.1] The microscopic interface surface ($\mathcal{S}_{\alpha\beta}$) between the α and β phases, is material to the extensive quantity flux of the phases.

[A.2] Very large Strouhal number ($St^{(\overline{e_\alpha}, \vartheta_c)} \gg 1$) where $St^{(\overline{e_\alpha}, \vartheta_c)} \left(\equiv \frac{L_c^{\overline{e_\alpha}}/t_c^{\overline{e_\alpha}}}{\vartheta_c} \right)$ is associated with the characteristic length increment ($L_c^{\overline{e_\alpha}}$) of the *REV* averaged $\overline{e_\alpha}^\alpha$ ($= \theta_\alpha \overline{e_\alpha}^\alpha$, θ_α - volume ratio of the α phase) quantity, its characteristic time step ($t_c^{\overline{e_\alpha}}$), and the characteristic velocity (ϑ_c) of the deforming surface enclosing the *REV*.

In view of (1), [A.1], [A.2] and [Bear & Bachmat, 1990], the general macroscopic balance equation for the α phase reads

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\theta_\alpha \overline{e_\alpha}^\alpha) = -\nabla \cdot \left[\theta_\alpha \left(\overline{e_\alpha}^\alpha \overline{\mathbf{V}_\alpha^m}^\alpha + \overline{\dot{e}_\alpha}^\alpha \overline{\mathbf{V}_\alpha^m}^\alpha - \overline{\mathbf{J}_\alpha^{Em}}^\alpha \right) \right] + \theta_\alpha \overline{\rho_\alpha \Gamma_\alpha^E}^\alpha , \quad (2)$$

in which ρ_α denotes the phase density, $\mathbf{V}_\alpha^m$ denotes its mass weighted velocity vector, $\mathbf{J}_\alpha^{Em}$ [$= e_\alpha (\mathbf{V}_\alpha^E - \mathbf{V}_\alpha^m)$] denotes the diffusive flux vector provided by an empirical relation (as $\mathbf{V}_\alpha^E$, the velocity of the phase extensive quantity, is a measurable quantity only for $E = \mathcal{U}$) and Γ_α^E denotes the rate of generating E per unit mass of the phase. Following [Sorek *et al.*, 2005] we argue that as the motion is not of a Brownian type, the vanishing of $\overline{e_\alpha}^\alpha$ will also cause the disappearance of $\dot{e}_\alpha$, leading to the assumption that [A.3] $\dot{e}_\alpha = \Lambda_{e_\alpha} \overline{e_\alpha}^\alpha$, in which Λ_{e_α} denotes a factor (e.g. obtained empirically) that can be a scalar, a component of a vector or of a tensor. In view of [A.3] and (2), we write

$$\overline{\dot{e}_\alpha}^\alpha \overline{\mathbf{V}_\alpha^m}^\alpha = \overline{\mathbf{A}_\alpha}^\alpha \overline{e_\alpha}^\alpha \overline{\mathbf{V}_\alpha^m}^\alpha , \quad \overline{\mathbf{A}_\alpha}^\alpha \equiv \overline{\Lambda_{e_\alpha} \mathbf{V}_\alpha^m}^\alpha . \quad (3)$$

By virtue of (3) and assuming that, [A.4] $|\overline{e_\alpha}^\alpha \overline{\mathbf{V}_\alpha^m}^\alpha| \gg |\overline{\dot{e}_\alpha}^\alpha \overline{\mathbf{V}_\alpha^m}^\alpha|$, the advective flux is dominant in comparison with the dispersive flux, we further assume [A.5] $1 \gg \|\overline{\mathbf{A}_\alpha}^\alpha\| \equiv \varepsilon$ suggesting that $\overline{\mathbf{A}_\alpha}^\alpha = \varepsilon \overline{\mathbf{B}_\alpha}^\alpha$ with $\|\overline{\mathbf{B}_\alpha}^\alpha\| = 1$. On the basis of [A.4], [A.5] and (3), we rewrite (2) the general macroscopic balance equation in the form

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\theta_\alpha \overline{e_\alpha}^\alpha) = -\nabla \cdot \left\{ \theta_\alpha \left[(\mathbf{I} + \varepsilon \overline{\mathbf{B}_\alpha}^\alpha) \overline{e_\alpha}^\alpha \overline{\mathbf{V}_\alpha^m}^\alpha - \overline{\mathbf{J}_\alpha^{Em}}^\alpha \right] \right\} + \theta_\alpha \overline{\rho_\alpha \Gamma_\alpha^E}^\alpha , \quad (4)$$

in which $\mathbf{I}$ denotes the unit tensor.

In [Sorek *et al.*, 2005] when considering the phase momentum ($E \equiv \mathbf{M}_\alpha$) for $e_\alpha = \rho_\alpha \mathbf{V}_\alpha^m$, $\mathbf{J}_\alpha^{M_\alpha^m} = \boldsymbol{\sigma}_\alpha$ ($\boldsymbol{\sigma}_\alpha$ - phase stress tensor), $\Gamma_\alpha^E = \mathbf{F}_\alpha$ ($\mathbf{F}_\alpha$ - specific body force acting on the phase) and assuming that, [A.6] $|\overline{\rho_\alpha^\alpha \mathbf{V}_\alpha^m}| \gg |\overline{\rho_\alpha^\alpha \mathbf{V}_\alpha^m}| \equiv |\overline{\mathbf{d}_\alpha^M}|$ (the intensive macroscopic momentum is dominant in comparison to the deviation from this quantity) we obtain in view of (4) the α phase *dominant momentum balance equation*

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\theta_\alpha \overline{\rho_\alpha^\alpha \mathbf{V}_\alpha^m}) = -\nabla \cdot (\theta_\alpha \overline{\rho_\alpha^\alpha \mathbf{V}_\alpha^m \mathbf{V}_\alpha^m} - \theta_\alpha \overline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}_\alpha^\alpha}) + \theta_\alpha \overline{\rho_\alpha^\alpha \mathbf{F}_\alpha^\alpha}, \quad (5)$$

and its *secondary momentum balance equation* in the form

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\theta_\alpha \overline{\mathbf{d}_\alpha^M}) = -\nabla \cdot [\theta_\alpha (\mathbf{I} + \boldsymbol{\Omega}_\alpha) \overline{\mathbf{d}_\alpha^M \mathbf{V}_\alpha^m}], \quad \boldsymbol{\Omega}_\alpha \equiv \overline{\boldsymbol{\Lambda}_{(\rho_\alpha V_\alpha^m)} \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_{V_\alpha^m}^\alpha} (\Lambda_{\rho_\alpha} \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_{V_\alpha^m})^{-1}, \quad (6)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\Lambda}_{(\rho_\alpha V_\alpha^m)}$ is related to Λ_{ρ_α} and $\boldsymbol{\Lambda}_{V_\alpha^m}$. We note in [Sorek *et al.*, 2005] that (5) associated with the larger spatial scale and (6) which is assumed of a much smaller order of magnitude at an adjacent smaller spatial scale, are coupled via $\overline{\mathbf{V}_\alpha^m}$ and that each is based on a different premise and thus can represent different characteristics. At the larger spatial scale, (5) can conform to a momentum balance equation that governs the propagation of shock waves through porous media [Levy *et al.*, 1995], to Forchheimer's law or to Darcy's law when friction at the solid-fluid interface is dominant. Concurrently, at an adjacent smaller spatial scale (i.e. in comparison to the *REV* scale), (6) represents a momentum flux governed by inertia that conforms to a wave equation propagating the $\overline{\mathbf{d}_\alpha^M}$ quantity.

Let γ denote a solute for which m^γ denotes its mass, C_α^γ denotes its concentration and ω_α^γ denotes its mass fraction in the α phase. Considering $E \equiv m^\gamma$, $e_\alpha^\gamma \equiv C_\alpha^\gamma = \omega_\alpha^\gamma \rho_\alpha$, $\mathbf{J}^{m^\gamma}$ and by virtue of (2), we write the macroscopic mass balance equation for γ in α to read

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} [\theta_\alpha (\overline{\omega_\alpha^\gamma \rho_\alpha^\alpha} + \overline{\dot{\omega}_\alpha^\gamma \dot{\rho}_\alpha^\alpha})] = -\nabla \cdot [\theta_\alpha (\overline{\omega_\alpha^\gamma \rho_\alpha^\alpha} + \overline{\dot{\omega}_\alpha^\gamma \dot{\rho}_\alpha^\alpha}) \overline{\mathbf{V}_\alpha^m} - \theta_\alpha \mathbf{D}_h \overline{\nabla C_\alpha^\gamma}] + \theta_\alpha \overline{\rho_\alpha^\alpha \Gamma^\gamma}. \quad (7)$$

We note that (7) does not account for [A.4] (i.e. $\overline{\omega_\alpha^\gamma \rho_\alpha^\alpha \mathbf{V}_\alpha^m} \cong \overline{C_\alpha^\gamma \mathbf{V}_\alpha^m} = \overline{[\omega_\alpha^\gamma \rho_\alpha^\alpha] \mathbf{V}_\alpha^m}$) and it follows Fick's law (i.e. the summation of the solute's dispersion ($\overline{C_\alpha^\gamma \mathbf{V}_\alpha^m}$) and diffusion ($\overline{\mathbf{J}_\alpha^{m^\gamma}}$) mass fluxes is related to $-\mathbf{D}_h \overline{\nabla C_\alpha^\gamma}$, where $\mathbf{D}_h$ denotes the hydrodynamic dispersion tensor). In view of (7) and by virtue of [A.3] we write

$$\overline{\dot{\omega}_\alpha^\gamma \dot{\rho}_\alpha^\alpha} = \overline{A_{C^\lambda}^\alpha \omega_\alpha^\gamma \rho_\alpha^\alpha}, \quad \overline{A_{C^\lambda}^\alpha} \equiv \overline{\Lambda_{\omega^\gamma} \Lambda_{\rho_\alpha}^\alpha}. \quad (8)$$

Following [A.6] we now assume [A.7] $\overline{\omega_\alpha^\gamma \rho_\alpha^\alpha} \gg \overline{\dot{\omega}_\alpha^\gamma \dot{\rho}_\alpha^\alpha}$ which in view of [A.5] and (8) we assume [A.8] $1 \gg |\overline{A_{C^\lambda}^\alpha}| \equiv \varepsilon$, suggesting that $\overline{A_{C^\lambda}^\alpha} = \varepsilon \overline{B_{C^\lambda}^\alpha}$ where $|\overline{B_{C^\lambda}^\alpha}| = 1$ so that (7) can be rewritten in the form

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\theta_\alpha \overline{\omega_\alpha^\gamma \rho_\alpha^\alpha}) + \varepsilon \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\theta_\alpha \overline{B_{C^\lambda}^\alpha \omega_\alpha^\gamma \rho_\alpha^\alpha}) &= -\nabla \cdot [\theta_\alpha (\overline{\omega_\alpha^\gamma \rho_\alpha^\alpha \mathbf{V}_\alpha^m} - \mathbf{D}_h \overline{\nabla C_\alpha^\gamma})] \\ &+ \theta_\alpha \overline{\rho_\alpha^\alpha \Gamma^\gamma} - \varepsilon \nabla \cdot (\theta_\alpha \overline{B_{C^\lambda}^\alpha \omega_\alpha^\gamma \rho_\alpha^\alpha \mathbf{V}_\alpha^m}) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Since the solution of (9) is a function of $\varepsilon \ll 1$, we can expand (see also [Sorek *et al.*, 2005]) the dependent variables of (9) using terms associated with a polynomial of ε powers. An approximate solution to (9) can thus be obtained by solving an infinite set of solute's mass balance equations of descending order magnitudes. While the first (i.e. when $\varepsilon = 0$) balance

equation may be nonlinear [e.g. when $\overline{\rho_\alpha^\alpha} = \overline{\rho_\alpha^\alpha(\overline{\omega_\alpha^\alpha})}$] and of the highest order of magnitude, the others are linear balance equations as they are combined with variables obtained from the solution of the equations that are of higher order magnitude. In view of (9) we thus assume that the *dominant solute mass balance equation* reads

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\theta_\alpha \overline{\omega_\alpha^\alpha} \overline{\rho_\alpha^\alpha} \right) = -\nabla \cdot \left[\theta_\alpha \left(\overline{\omega_\alpha^\alpha} \overline{\rho_\alpha^\alpha} \overline{\mathbf{V}_\alpha^{m^\alpha}} - \mathbf{D}_h \nabla C_\alpha^{\gamma^\alpha} \right) \right] + \theta_\alpha \overline{\rho_\alpha^\alpha} \Gamma^{\gamma^\alpha}, \quad (10)$$

and the *secondary solute mass balance equation* becomes

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\theta_\alpha \overline{d_\alpha^{m^\alpha}} \right) = -\nabla \cdot \left(\theta_\alpha \overline{d_\alpha^{m^\alpha}} \overline{\mathbf{V}_\alpha^{m^\alpha}} \right), \quad \overline{d_\alpha^{m^\alpha}} \equiv \overline{\omega_\alpha^\alpha} \overline{\rho_\alpha^\alpha}. \quad (11)$$

Both macroscopic solute mass balance equations (10) and (11) are coupled via $\overline{\mathbf{V}_\alpha^{m^\alpha}}$. At the larger spatial scale (10) accounts mass fluxes characterized by advection and hydrodynamic dispersion. At the adjacent scale, smaller than the one considered for spatial averaging, the mass balance of $\overline{d_\alpha^{m^\alpha}}$ is described by a pure advection mechanism. Hence at the smaller spatial scale the solute migration is governed by two coupled macroscopic equations, pure advection described by (11) and a wave equation (6) as the driving force.

In what follows we refer to observations that consider the migration of colloidal particles.

2. FIELD OBSERVATIONS

Field observations under natural gradient flow conditions (specific discharge of 4 to 16m/yr and 35% porosity) in a contaminated sandy aquifer show, microscale Eulerian variations in the flux, mineralogical composition and size of suspended particles [Ronen *et al.*, 1992, Weisbrod *et al.*, 1996]. Along a 16m saturated section below the water table the average concentration of particles in groundwater varied between 1 and 40mg/L, but high concentrations of up to 5,000mg/L were also detected. The particles were composed of CaCO₃ (11 – 57%) quartz (7 – 39%) and clays (8 – 43%). Most of the particles were within the 140 – 3000nm size range with size modes varying from 310 to 660nm. The large amounts of suspended particles are considered to be related to the high inputs of dissolved organic carbon into groundwater from sewage effluents which have been used for agricultural irrigation since the early 1960s. As a result of organic matter biodegradation at the saturated unsaturated interface region, anoxic conditions developed and the pCO₂ content of groundwater increased dramatically (pCO₂ = 10^{-1.8} to 10^{-1.3}). It is postulated that part of the carbonate cement of the rocks dissolved and detrital CaCO₃, quartz and clays were released as colloidal particles. In the prevailing anoxic conditions of groundwater at the study site (dissolved oxygen < 1mg/L), colloidal stability is enhanced by organic matter coating of particles.

The transport of large amounts of particles under the above mentioned natural flow conditions within a porous medium (average grain size of 125μm) is striking. Motion of different particle parcels observed along the depth of a well and sampled at different time periods, under natural flow conditions and due to a pumping excitation, are depicted in Figure 1. In view of this finding we postulate that upon the start of pumping (100L/min), inertia temporally governs the flow regime (wave motion at the first instant [Sorek, 1996]) at the large spatial scale causing the rise of colloids turbidity. The large scale flow regime can be dominated by Darcy's flow or temporally driven by inertia represented in the form of shock

Figure 1: Particles concentration at different sampling time (days) intervals along a well depth, under natural flow conditions and due to a pumping ($100L/min$) excitation

waves [Sorek *et al.*, 2005]. Concurrently, a bulk of colloids with a decreased turbidity is filtered through the smaller space scale, driven by the combination of wave influenced motion and pure advective transport mechanisms governed by (6) and (11) respectively. Observations at different time periods demonstrating different dominant mean size of particles across depth appear in Figure 2. The displacement of different center of particles mass through corresponding microscopic pathline networks, suggest a mass bulk displacement which is characteristic to wave influenced motion and pure advective mechanism.

Figure 2: Particle size distribution for sampling intervals of two profiles

3. CONCLUSION

The fluid microscopic momentum equation and the solute mass balance equation are averaged with respect to the *REV* spatial scale. Each balance equation is proven to be built of two coupled macroscopic equations, one assumed dominant as it is composed of averaged extensive quantities and one assumed to be secondary addressing a smaller spatial scale as it is composed of extensive quantities deviating from the averaged ones. The secondary macroscopic balance equations are habitually neglected, yet these can be significant in cases of deviation from the average fluid velocities and/or for heterogeneity in fluid properties.

A feasible possibility is that at the larger spatial scale the dominant macroscopic fluid momentum follows the drag dominated linear momentum in the form of Darcy's law and the dominant solute mass balance refers to a continuous stirring-and-transport mechanism that is characterized by hydrodynamic dispersion and advective fluxes. Concurrently, at the smaller spatial scale the secondary fluid macroscopic momentum balance describes a wave motion and the secondary macroscopic solute mass balance abides pure advective transport.

Based on these theoretical findings we postulate that the temporal and spatial distribution associated with the mobility of colloidal particles can be evaluated by the fluid momentum governed by (11) and the solute mass flux governed by (6). If this hypothesis is correct, it can be envisaged that after been formed, colloidal particles are easily transported within porous media. We provide observations evidence indicating an increase in turbidity at the instant of starting to pump a well, namely when the flow regime is changed. In reference to (5) and following [Sorek, 1996], the flow regime in the large spatial scale can temporally be governed by inertia that drives the particles into higher turbidity while their mass balance equation will account for advection and dispersion fluxes. Observations after operation of the pump indicate that turbidity decreases and the particles are gathered into a bulk motion which is characteristic of pure advection and a driving force associated with wave motion.

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